

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B320
Date: 21 August 2007
Take Off 09:45:37Z 16:06:32Z
Landing: 14:41:59Z 17:19:20Z
Flight Time 4h56m22s 1h12m48s

Campaign: CAESAR

Operating Area: NW Approaches with refuel at Stornoway

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM 1	Dawn Quinn	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Chawn Harlow	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Mo Smith	FAAM
6	Core Chemistry / Drospondes / CCM2	Doug Anderson	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics	Kate Turnbull	FAAM
8	SWS & SHIMS Training	Debbie O'Sullivan	Met Office
9	SWS & Nephelometer	Andy Wilson	Met Office
10	ARIES	Stuart Newman	Met Office
11	MARSS / DEIMOS	Dave Pollard	Met Office
12	Mission Scientist 2	Paul Barrett	Met Office
13	TAFTS	Paul Green	Imperial College
14			
15			
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18			
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20			

Flight Track:

B320 Track 21-AUG-07

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B320
 Date: 21 August 2007
 Project: CAESAR Cirrus
 Location: NW Approaches

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
082940		Start-Up	0.32 kft	125	52'04.36N, 0'37.48W
094537		T/O	1.4 kft	031	Cranfield
100014		Video	26.0 kft		Start FFC & RFC
112609	113819	Profile 1	26.0 - 32.1 kft	356	
113117		Video	29.5 kft	357	Change tapes
113820	113932	Run 1.1	32.1 - 32.0 kft	027	
114052	115102	Run 1.1	31.0 kft	028	
115015		Event	31.0 kft	027	Under contrail
115547	120554	Run 1.2	31.1 - 31.0 kft	220	Below Cirrus
120636	120928	Orbit 1	31.0 kft	256	35deg right, from 270
121026	121317	Orbit 2	31.1 - 30.9 kft	289	35deg right
121516	122243	Profile 2	31.1 - 34.0 kft	027	R2 In Cirrus
122243	123243	Run 2	34.0 kft	023	R2 In Cirrus
123159		Sonde	34.0 kft	023	Launch #01
123634		Sonde	34.0 kft	215	Launch #02
123647	123847	Profile 3	34.0 - 35.0 kft	215	Contrailing
123847	124846	Run 3.1	35.0 kft	213	
123906		Sonde	35.0 kft	213	Launch #03
124026		Event	35.0 kft	212	Contrailing
124513		Sonde	35.0 kft	211	Launch #04
125130	130132	Run 3.2	35.0 kft	019	
130350	131715	Profile 4	35.1 - 23.0 kft	222	
130419		Video	34.7 kft	215	Change tapes
131925	132314	Profile 4	23.0 - 20.0 kft	022	
132315	133332	Run 4	20.0 - 20.1 kft	028	
132434		Video	20.0 kft	026	Switch to UFC & DFC
133409	133527	Orbit 3	20.0 - 20.1 kft	313	60deg left, from 310
133623	133733	Orbit 4	20.2 - 20.0 kft	229	60deg left, from 240
133825	133934	Orbit 5	20.2 - 20.1 kft	140	60deg left, from 130
134059	134833	Profile 5	20.0 - 12.0 kft	219	1200fpm
135030	140126	Profile 5	12.1 - 0.62 kft	024	Interrupt @1k', QNH 1027
140258	140543	Profile 5	0.62 - -.38 kft	207	1k'-50', Q1029
140555	141600	Run 5	-.33 - -.34 kft	210	
141340		Heimann	-.34 kft	190	Cal, SST 13.3C
143817		Video	3.1 kft	156	End of tapes
144159		Land	-.38 kft	286	Stornoway
144749		Shutdown	-.37 kft	041	58'12.85N, 6'19.26W

B320 Track 21-AUG-07

FAAM Sortie Brief

CAESAR flight - Radiative properties of cirrus

Flight no: B320

Date: 21st August 2007

Take Off: 0930Z (10:30 local). Refuel required.

Aim:

The aim of this sortie is to determine the radiative properties of frontal or convective cirrus using multiple frequencies from the range of remote sensing instruments on the aircraft. For closure it is also important to determine the in-situ properties of the cloud and to make radiative measurements of the atmosphere above and below the cirrus. To obtain in-situ vertical distributions perform profile ascents and descents. Ideally measurements should be made advecting with the wind, such that the same air mass is continuously measured, unless the generation site is stable. Straight and level runs should be made below, above and in the cirrus. A 100ft run over the sea will be required to measure the SST. Orbits are to be made below the cloud with SWS viewing upwards to determine the phase function of the ice particles.

Satellite Overpass:

AQUA (AIRS): 1239Z

Large AIRS swath so exact location not critical. Ideally be above the cirrus viewing nadir during the overpass time.

Weather conditions:

Clear sky below the layer of cirrus in the measurement area is essential. Ideally the cirrus should not extend above 35,000ft.

Location:

Over sea only. North Scotland

Clearances:

NOTAM areas C&D will be required for dropping sondes and runs at 100ft.

Instruments required:

Critical: ARIES, SWS, SID1, SID2, 2DC, Temp, Humidity (especially FWVS at high alt), AVAPS.
Desirable: MARSS, TAFTS, SHIMS, Heimann, FFSSP, 2DP, CIPs, Heimann, Core chem (auto mode OK).

Operational instructions:

Nev

- when out of cloud in a straight and level run zero it

ARIES and SWS

- Both instruments must point in the same direction (either zenith or nadir) as each other, except during cal. ARIES needs to tell SWS where it is pointing.
- Majority of time should be towards the cloud (or sea at 100ft), however, still need some data pointing away to characterise the atmosphere above and below the cloud (e.g. ~2 of 10 min run)
- For orbits both instruments should view towards cloud for whole time
- When close to the area of operation (~15mins) take data during both transits

ARIES

- If it is still unstable for zenith views (shutter open) at high altitudes, it is better to get 1 min of good data in a 10 min run (with rest of time with shutter closed viewing cal or nadir) than all bad data – let SWS know which viewing direction and when.

SWS

- Continue to take data during the profiles
- Ensure that the signal does not saturate. Request extra orbits if necessary.

	Time (Z)	Manoeuvre	Duration (min)	Total time (min)
1	0930	Takeoff from Cranfield & transit at appropriate level	120	120
2	1130	Fly 1 straight and level reciprocal run 1000ft below cirrus, orientated across wind, each of 10 mins. Each leg ideally containing majority ci, but with one end in clear sky.	10	130
3	1140	Fly two orbits below cloud at 55deg (or max) banking angle.	10	140
4	1150	Profile ascent into cirrus	15	155
5	1205	Fly one straight and level run in cloud, orientated across wind, of 10 mins	10	165
8	1215	Profile ascent to 1000ft above cirrus top or max alt	15	180
9	1230	Fly two straight and level reciprocal runs 1000ft above cirrus, orientated across wind, each of 10 mins. Drop 3 sondes spread along one run so that they are in the air during the satellite overpass (1239Z)	20	200
12	1250	Profile descent to 1000ft below cloud base	10	210
13	1300	Fly one straight and level run 1000ft below cirrus base, orientated across wind, of 10 mins.	10	220
14	1310	Perform two orbits at 55deg (or max) banking angle below cirrus (critical manoeuvre – if time is tight miss out points 10 to 13 instead)	10	230
15	1320	Profile descent to 100ft (interrupted when necessary) (critical)	35	265
16	1355	Straight and level run of 10 mins duration at 100 ft over sea only. (critical)	10	275
17	1405	Transit to refuel point	30	305
18	1435	Land for refuel	total =	305
19	~1700	Take off		
20	~1800	Land at Cranfield	60	60

AQUA (AIRS) overpass

AQUA 2007/08/21 AQUA ORBITAL PREDICT PLOT EPOCH DATE: 07/06/04
■ lat: 51.57 slon: 358.69 AIRS swath angle: 47.3 deg res: 9 km

B320- Flight De-Brief

21/08/07

Mission Scientist: Chawn Harlow

Campaign: CAESAR

This was a successful CAESAR sortie with appreciable cirrus above an otherwise clear atmosphere. The flight started with a 100 min transit to the operating area where the conditions were found to be ideal near the NW corner of NOTAM Area C. A series of SLR's were carried out: 1000 ft below the cirrus at FL310; in the cirrus at FL340; skimming in/out of the tops of the cirrus at FL350; underneath the cirrus at FL200; and at 100' above the sea surface. Refuel occurred at Stornoway on the Isle of Lewis.

SWS and ARIES coordinated on viewing direction with a majority of the high level runs in the direction of cloud and the low level run focusing on the sea surface. Views of zenith during the low level run by ARIES and SWS were concurrent with the Heimann calibration. 2 and 3 orbits were carried out at FL310 and FL200 achieving a bank angle of 35° and 60°, respectively. Cirrus was observed to fill the nadir fields of view throughout all of the orbits. An extra 60° orbit was carried out at FL200 at request of the SWS operator. Four sondes were dropped : Three were in flight at overpass time and the fourth was dropped ~six minutes after overpass. The first sonde had intermittent communications and thus an addition sonde was dropped to assure that good profile information is available. Other instrumental issues occurred with the General Eastern Hygrometer and TAFTS producing data of questionable quality.

One difficult call was necessary during the sortie: The choice to do the second set of SLR and orbits at FL200 instead of FL310. This was motivated by the inability of the aircraft to achieve greater than 35° angle of bank at FL310. FL200 was the greatest height that maximum bank angle could be achieved while maintaining a steady orbit without losing altitude. It is believed that cirrus filled the field of view of the radiometers during all of the orbits.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B..... 320 Date 21/08/07..... Name Chawn Harlow..... Page 1..... of 3.....

Time (Z)	Cloud Type/ Amount (oktas)	Weather	Visibility (kms)	Wind direction°/ Speed(kts)	Remarks
					Special features – Position, Run/Profile, Height, Heading Events - Instrument problems, Change plan/ Operating Area
0946	SCu 8/8	Lt. rain		/	T/O Cranfield
1030 ish				/	SWS fine
				/	Deimos Down MARSS Ch. 16 Down
				/	Aries fine
				/	Tafts No good
				/	GE DP not set (post-process req)
				/	CIP US
				/	SID1 + SID2 OK
				/	AVAPS OK
				/	FWVS - not good, may use bogus data from GE
112609				/	P1 Start FL260-FL 330
113820				/	P1 End FL320
				/	R1 Start - CPhys seeing particles
113922				/	R1 End
114052	Clear ↓ Ci ↑			/	R1.1 Start FL310
114233 ish				/	Passing under contrails!
115102				/	R1.1 End
115547				/	R1.2 Start Clear Below Ci Above
120554				/	R1.2 End
120636	120928			/	O1 35° Banked orbit
121026	121317			/	O2 " " "
121516				/	P2 St FL310 - FL340
122243				/	P2 End

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B..320 Date 21/08/07..... Name Chawn Harbu Page 2 of 3

Time (Z)	Cloud Type/ Amount (oktas)	Weather	Visibility (kms)	Wind direction°/ Speed(kts)	Remarks Special features – Position, Run/Profile, Height, Heading Events - Instrument problems, Change plan/ Operating Area
122243				/	R2 start In Ci
123243				/	R2. End
123159				/	Sonde 1 - Intermittant
123634				/	Sonde 2
123647				/	P3 Start
123847				/	P3 End R3.1 Start FL350
123906				/	Sonde 3
124513				/	Sonde 4.
124846				/	R3.1 End
125130				/	R3.2 Start Out of Ci
1254ish				/	Back in Ci
130132				/	R3.2 End
130350				/	P4 Start
131715				/	P4 Interrupt
131925				/	P4 Recommense
132314				/	P4 End
1326ish				/	Moving into region w/ thinner Ci above
1328				/	PCASP back online after descent
				/	Back under thicker Ci
132315				/	R4 Start FL 200
133332				/	R4 End
133409				/	03 St FL200 60° Bank angle
133623				/	04 St
133825				/	05 St

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B320

Date: 21/08/07 **Operator:** KFT **DRS Time:** 08:16:00 **DAU1 Time:** +0 **DAU2 Time:** +0 **DAU3 Time:** +0 **Aux1 Time:** +0 **Aux2 Time:** +0 **Page 1 of 1**

G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
09:50			restart										ON	U/S?		Heaters on	
09:59																M6X error on SID2	
	During transit, changed FFSSP signal/annulus base values as required to keep instrument running; 16< base >80, annulus > 80 PCASP flow noisy																
10:22																2DP rearm 2 1 as noisy	
10:29																SID1 restarted with filename b320 (not b000)	
11:26:09	41	0.10	359	0	0	0		NOISE								START P1 FL260	
11:27:18	22	0.08		1	0	0		NOISE								FL270	
11:28:37	20	0.09		0	0	0		NOISE								FL280	
11:30:10	32	0.10		0	0	0		NOISE								FL290	
11:32:15	29	0.15		0	0	0		NOISE								FL300	
11:34:09	3	0.14		0	0	0		NOISE								FL310	
11:37:57	32	0.14		8	20	0.5	25	NOISE				0				FL320	
11:40:52	11	0.08	360	1	0	0		NOISE							11	FL310 START RUN 1	
11:43:00	5	0.12		0	0	0		NOISE									
11:45:00	42	0.08		1	0	0		NOISE									
11:47:00	23	0.08		0	0	0		NOISE								SID2 LASER 14mW	
11:49:00	10	0.09		0	0	0		NOISE									
11:51:02	8	0.09		0	0	0		NOISE								END RUN 1	
11:55:00	10	0.09		0	0	0		NOISE									
11:55:47	14	0.09		0	0	0		NOISE								START RUN 1.2 FL310	
11:58:00	12	0.10		0	0	0		NOISE									
12:00:00	21	0.07		0	0	0		NOISE									
12:02:00	19	0.13		0	0	0		NOISE									
12:04:00	51	0.13		0	0	0		NOISE									
12:05:55	52	0.11		0	0	0		NOISE								END RUN 1.2	
12:06:36	8	0.10		0	0	0		NOISE								ORBIT 1 35deg bank	
12:09:31	3	0.11		0	0	0		NOISE								END ORBIT 1	
12:10:25	37	0.08		0	0	0		NOISE								ORBIT 2 35deg bank	
12:13:17	8	0.09		0	0	0		NOISE								END ORBIT 2	
12:15:17	17	0.11		0	0	0		NOISE								START PROFILE 2 FL310	
12:16:27	73	0.18		1	1	9		NOISE								FL320	
12:17:47	28	0.08		10	2	0.5	25	NOISE				0			11	FL325	
12:19:07	100	0.18	361	50	2	5	200	NOISE				0			11,8	FL330	
12:20:39	34	0.17		20	1	11	150	NOISE				0			11,8	FL335	
12:22:39	25	0.07		10	1	5	100	NOISE				0			11,8	FL340 START RUN 2	
12:25:00	42	0.22	362	20	2	2	200	NOISE				0			11,8		
12:27:00	37	0.20	363	100	8	11	150	NOISE				0			11,8		
12:28:30	75	0.12	366	300	10	2	150	NOISE				0			11,8		
12:30:00	22	0.13	367	100	10	47	125	NOISE				0			11,8		
12:32:00	34	0.13	368	20	2	13	100	NOISE				0			11,8	SONDE 1 FL340	
12:32:44	10	0.12		80	8	36	125	NOISE				0			11,8	END RUN 2.1	

PCASP Reference Volts = 8.3V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.2V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -1	CIP25 End element 1 voltage =	CIP100 End element 1 voltage =
PCASP Flow rate = 0.8		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -1	CIP25 End element 64 voltage =	CIP100 End element 64 voltage =
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = 12mW	2D2-P End element 1 voltage =		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B320

Date: 21/08/07 **Operator:** KFT **DRS Time:** 08:16:00 **DAU1 Time:** +0 **DAU2 Time:** +0 **DAU3 Time:** +0 **Aux1 Time:** +0 **Aux2 Time:** +0 **Page 2 of 2**

G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
12:34:00	15	0.20	369	20	8	11	200	0					0			11,8	FL340
12:36:00	23	0.11	370	100	10	87	125	0					0			11,8	
12:36:50	48	0.32	371	10	1	4	200	0					0	DATA?!		11,8	START PROFILE 3 FL330
12:38:47	30	0.43	372	10	1	3	150	0								11,8	SONDE 3 END P3 FL350, START R3
12:41:00	58	0.37		20	1	20	125	0					0.15			4/9	
12:43:00	47	0.17	373	20	1	2.5	100	0					0.14			11,8	
12:45:00	41	0.16		0	0	0											SONDE 4 FL350
12:47:00	54	0.16		0	0	0											
12:48:48	42	0.39		0	0	0							0.10		900		END RUN 3.1
12:51:30	76	0.68		0	0	0											START RUN 3.2 FL350
12:52:30																	PCASP OFF – VREF=0.3V
12:54:00	-	-	375	200	80	2.5	25	0					0.06		692		
12:56:00	-	-		10	2	1.5	200	0					0.02		389		
12:58:00	-	-	376	30	30	9.5	150	0					0.02		1211		
13:00:00	-	-	377	30	1	5	200	0					0.02		1249		
13:01:33	-	-	378	30	2	6	200	0					0.02		1289		END RUN 3.2
13:03:50	-	-		30	1	1.5	150	0							1646		START PROFILE 4 FL350
13:04:59	-	-	379	0	0	0		0									FL340
13:06:12	-	-		2	0	0		0									FL330
13:07:27	-	-		0	0	0		0									FL320
13:08:40	-	-		0	0	0		0									FL310 PCASP ON AGAIN VREF OCNL OK
13:09:50	-	-		0	0	0		0									FL300
13:10:55	-	-		0	0	0		0									FL290
13:11:59	-	-		0	0	0		0									FL280
12:13:09	-	-	918	0	0	0		0									FL270
13:15:00	303	0.09	2967	1	0	0		NOISE									FL250 FFSSP SYNCH'ED/ADJUSTED
13:17:12	351	0.08	2967	1	0	0		NOISE									FL230 PCASP VREF = 7V mostly
13:19:26	330	0.09	2967	0	0	0		NOISE									FL230
13:20:43	247	0.09	2968	1	0	0		NOISE									FL220
13:22:00	222	0.10		1	0	0		NOISE									FL210
13:23:13	151	0.08		0	0	0		NOISE									FL200 START RUN 4
13:25:00	73	0.08		0	0	0		NOISE									
13:27:00	31	0.12		3	0	0		NOISE									
13:29:00	6	0.07		1	0	0		0									PCASP VREF=7.7V (stable now)
13:31:00	8	0.13		1	0	0		0									
13:33:00	30	0.17		0	0	0		0									
13:35:27	37	0.20	2969	0	0	0		NOISE									END ORBIT 3 FL200
13:37:40	45	0.25		1	0	0		0									END ORBIT 4 FL200
13:39:34	20	0.16		1	0	0		NOISE									END ORBIT 5 FL200
																	Spurious SID2 signal during orbit? 10000 counts nothing else "sees"
13:41:02	16	0.08		1	0	0		0									START PROFILE 5 FL200
13:42:00	19	0.11		0	0	0		0									FL190
13:42:53	15	0.10		2	0	0		0									FL180

PCASP Reference Volts = 8.3V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.2V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -1	CIP25 End element 1 voltage =	CIP100 End element 1 voltage =
PCASP Flow rate = 0.8		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -1	CIP25 End element 64 voltage =	CIP100 End element 64 voltage =
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = 12mW	2D2-P End element 1 voltage =		

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B320 **T/O:** 09:45:37
Date of flight: 21/08/07 **Land:** 14:41:59

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		To Exeter to process
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B320
Date of Flight: 21/08/07

B) 2D PROCESSING		REPROCESS +1hr
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC	Y	
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)	Y	
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	Y	15809 blocks
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) Unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip	Y	Size of Bnnn.dat = 181321
6) FLOODS> WAVE WAVE> CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat WAVE> exit	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section Blocks read = 51267 Blocks written = 51267 Bad reads = 0
7) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 5 min)</i> f) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land + 5 min)</i> g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data: Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N	Y	Start = 094000 End = 144500 Ignore error message scroll (vestigial error from tapes) Are FRW, FSP, IMB, PCA,SEC files in PMSDATA? Y Are they non-zero in size? Y
8) FLOODS> WAVE i). WAVE> imagedisplay a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) File generation no: 0 d) Time from IWC plot: N e) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP f) Start time: <i>As in 7e above</i> g) End time: <i>As in 7f above</i> h) Time interval (sec): 5 recommended (0 for all images) ii). WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 1 min)</i> e) Enter end time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 1 min)</i> f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks: 10 iii). WAVE> exit to create files iv). FTP ascii *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC v). Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter vi). Output as pdf file (720 dpi resolution), appending name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files	Y	2D image display and printing Must be done from FLOODS itself. Note any problems with images 2dc last image 1304 2dp noise only from 1020 Prepare imagery for Core data From own PC again Start = 094000 End = 144500, 110000 FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_ Bnnn_2Dx-images.ps Notes on this in instructions 13pp 2DC 11pp 2DP (only to 103000)

<p>9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>	Y	<p>NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful.</p> <p>X = b320_tas</p> <p>Start = 094500 End = 144200</p> <p>Time data processed to = 133900 2dproc files present? Y *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat</p>
<p>10) FLOODS> WAVE</p> <p>i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' ii). exit</p>	Y	<p>Use PVWAVE for this section</p> <p>Error message about HDDR file should be ignored.</p> <p>Records = 5678, 178</p>
<p>11) FLOODS> MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>	Y	<p>X = b320_tas Y = (X+1) = b320_tas_2d</p>
<p>12) CHECKS:</p> <p>Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i></p>	N	<p>Data present in _tas_2d</p> <p>Correlated?</p>

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B320
Date of Flight: 21/08/07

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	Y	
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i> <i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i> e) Calibration volume flow rate: <i>Use the most recent value. 1.8ccs⁻¹</i> <i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i> <i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i> f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i> g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i> h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>	Y	Min size = 1 Vol flow rate = 0.8 094500 144200
3) FLOODS> WAVE i).WAVE> write_procpcasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp' ii). WAVE> exit	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section
4) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>	Y	X = _tas Y = X+1 = _tas_2dpcasp
5) CHECKS Are PCASP and JW peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Neph – total blue scatter.</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>	N	Data present in tas_2dpcasp Merged OK?

FAAM Dropsonde Flight Log

Flight No.	B320	Date	21 Aug 2007	Operator	Doug Anderson	Page No.	1 of 1
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GMT	Sonde No.	Event <i>eg land, splashdown</i>	Comments <i>pressure hPa, T deg C, RH %, wind direction deg, wind speed m/s, longitude, latitude, height m</i>
12:32:03	1	Launch	249.60 -50.70 999.00 340.30 34.30 -16.60 -7.645400 60.551100 10371.70
12:44:09	1	Splashdown	1027.95 11.05 81.18 266.61 2.87 -10.28 -7.543755 60.483570 99999.00
12:37:03	2	Launch	247.50 -51.30 999.00 319.10 29.40 -15.80 -8.072200 60.565200 10426.30
12:48:54	2	Splashdown	1028.18 11.02 84.03 235.32 2.38 -10.62 -7.915284 60.547070 99999.00
12:39:09	3	Launch	239.20 -10.69 1.00 22.35 151.76 0.12 -8.266569 60.366385 99999.00
12:51:43	3	Splashdown	1027.98 11.56 78.86 245.68 2.51 -11.41 -8.158483 60.298576 99999.00
12:45:15	4	Launch	238.00 -52.70 999.00 325.60 30.30 -17.40 -8.832100 59.728700 10677.80
12:57:20	4	Splashdown	1028.86 12.06 999.00 286.96 1.88 -10.29 -8.721428 59.707764 99999.00

B320_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog.txt

```

10:06:28.74 --- - - - -
10:06:28.74 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
10:06:28.74 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
      tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
10:06:28.74 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B320
10:06:28.74 --- - - - -
10:07:33.30 --- - - - -
10:07:33.30 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
10:07:33.30 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
      tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
10:07:33.30 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B320
10:07:33.30 --- - - - -
10:07:38.03 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
10:07:55.16 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
10:08:00.63 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
10:08:01.76 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
10:08:21.31 SWS - 100 - - Sample period changed from 500ms to 100ms.
10:08:23.65 USH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 500ms to 100ms.
10:08:25.97 LSH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 500ms to 100ms.
10:08:32.15 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:08:32.16 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:08:32.16 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:08:40.51 SWS - - 50 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 50ms.
10:08:43.28 SWS - - - 50 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 50ms.
10:08:46.65 USH - - 50 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 50ms.
10:08:48.90 USH - - - 50 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 50ms.
10:08:51.39 LSH - - 50 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 50ms.
10:08:54.49 LSH - - - 80 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 80ms.
10:08:57.21 LSH - - 80 - VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 80ms.
10:09:00.09 LSH - - 90 - VIS int.time changed from 80ms to 90ms.
10:09:03.14 LSH - - - 90 NIR int.time changed from 80ms to 90ms.
10:09:06.48 USH - - - 80 NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 80ms.
10:09:09.41 USH - - - 90 NIR int.time changed from 80ms to 90ms.
10:09:15.68 USH - - 90 - VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 90ms.
10:09:56.21 SWS - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
10:09:59.24 SWS - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
10:10:03.39 SWS - - - 750 NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 750ms.
10:10:08.82 USH - - - 500 NIR int.time changed from 90ms to 500ms.
10:10:18.49 USH - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 100ms.
10:10:21.82 USH - - - 90 NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 90ms.
10:10:24.61 SWS - - - 90 NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 90ms.
10:10:26.88 SWS - - 90 - VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 90ms.
10:10:32.60 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:10:32.61 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:10:32.63 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:10:33.96 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:10:34.21 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:10:34.36 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:10:44.08 LSH - - - - Idling
10:10:44.08 USH - - - - Idling
10:10:44.10 SWS - - - - Idling
10:10:46.94 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:10:46.96 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:10:46.96 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:10:48.29 SWS - - - - Idling
10:10:48.50 LSH - - - - Idling
10:10:48.71 USH - - - - Idling
10:10:54.51 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
10:11:04.21 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
10:11:08.46 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
10:11:13.88 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:11:13.88 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:11:13.88 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:11:15.21 USH - - - - Idling
10:11:15.42 LSH - - - - Idling
10:11:15.62 SWS - - - - Idling
10:11:21.58 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.

```

10:11:21.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:11:21.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:13:34.99	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
10:13:58.17	---	-	-	-	-	*** playing with software in transit
11:00:56.06	---	-	-	-	-	
11:00:56.06	---	-	-	-	-	+++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
11:00:56.06	---	-	-	-	-	+++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period / tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
11:00:56.06	---	-	-	-	-	+++ Flight no. B320
11:00:56.06	---	-	-	-	-	
11:00:59.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS FAILED NIR FAILED
11:04:57.26	---	-	-	-	-	
11:04:57.26	---	-	-	-	-	+++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
11:04:57.26	---	-	-	-	-	+++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period / tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
11:04:57.26	---	-	-	-	-	+++ Flight no. B320
11:04:57.26	---	-	-	-	-	
11:05:06.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
11:05:10.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
11:05:12.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
11:05:24.68	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:05:28.24	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:05:39.86	SWS	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 500ms to 100ms.
11:05:42.64	USH	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 500ms to 100ms.
11:05:45.48	LSH	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 500ms to 100ms.
11:05:50.07	SWS	-	-	60	-	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 60ms.
11:05:52.86	SWS	-	-	-	60	NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 60ms.
11:05:55.37	USH	-	-	60	-	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 60ms.
11:05:57.70	USH	-	-	-	60	NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 60ms.
11:06:01.78	LSH	-	-	60	-	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 60ms.
11:06:04.40	LSH	-	-	-	60	NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 60ms.
11:06:07.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:06:11.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:06:13.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:06:27.37	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:09:12.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:09:12.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:09:12.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:09:13.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:09:13.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:09:13.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:17:45.48	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
11:17:51.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:17:51.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:17:52.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:17:52.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:17:53.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:17:53.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:17:56.41	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:17:59.61	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:18:04.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:18:05.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:18:07.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:18:07.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:18:07.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:18:08.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:18:08.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:18:09.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:18:12.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:18:12.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:18:12.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:18:50.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:18:50.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:18:50.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:18:51.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:18:52.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:18:52.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:19:35.41	---	-	-	-	-	*** looking at sc sheet below from FL260
11:22:15.04	---	-	-	-	-	*** clear slot below - just the sea to see

```

11:26:30.19 --- - - - - *** start of profile 1
11:30:58.55 SWS 6F - - - - Telescope position set to 6F
11:31:21.75 --- - - - - *** very thin cirrus above
11:38:31.35 --- - - - - *** end of profilr climb start run 1.1
11:39:39.43 --- - - - - *** end of run
11:39:57.04 SWS - - 90 - VIS int.time changed from 60ms to 90ms.
11:40:00.82 SWS - - - 90 NIR int.time changed from 60ms to 90ms.
11:40:04.54 LSH - - 90 - VIS int.time changed from 60ms to 90ms.
11:40:08.11 LSH - - - 90 NIR int.time changed from 60ms to 90ms.
11:40:12.13 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:40:12.15 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:40:12.17 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:40:12.66 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:40:13.22 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:40:13.88 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:40:14.09 LSH - - - - Idling
11:40:19.51 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:41:02.21 --- - - - - *** run at 310
11:42:44.55 --- - - - - *** just flew under some contrails
11:44:44.75 USH - - - - Idling
11:44:44.84 LSH - - - - Idling
11:44:44.86 SWS - - - - Idling
11:44:46.61 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
11:44:49.81 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:44:49.81 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:44:49.84 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:44:50.33 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:44:50.54 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:45:06.98 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:45:07.01 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:45:07.10 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:45:08.27 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:45:08.34 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:45:08.71 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:48:23.78 SWS 174R - - - - Telescope position set to 174R
11:49:19.21 --- - - - - *** end of run at FL 310
11:49:46.31 --- - - - - *** not yet
11:51:03.95 --- - - - - *** now
11:52:20.25 SWS 6F - - - - Telescope position set to 6F
11:55:58.68 --- - - - - *** start of run 1.2
12:01:23.27 SWS 174R - - - - Telescope position set to 174R
12:04:12.51 SWS 6F - - - - Telescope position set to 6F
12:04:12.93 SWS 6F - - - - Telescope position set to 6F
12:05:55.76 --- - - - - *** end of run 1.2
12:06:23.97 --- - - - - *** turning to right
12:06:33.67 SWS - - - - Idling
12:06:33.67 LSH - - - - Idling
12:06:33.69 USH - - - - Idling
12:06:35.12 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:06:35.13 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:06:35.13 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:06:36.46 SWS - - - - Idling
12:06:36.58 USH - - - - Idling
12:06:36.66 LSH - - - - Idling
12:06:36.79 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:06:36.79 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:06:36.81 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:06:49.07 --- - - - - *** orbit 1
12:09:18.37 --- - - - - *** end of orbit 1 35 deg bank angle sza 48
                                deg
12:09:34.35 LSH - - - - Idling
12:09:34.37 SWS - - - - Idling
12:09:34.39 USH - - - - Idling
12:09:35.87 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:09:35.88 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:09:35.88 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:09:37.50 USH - - - - Idling
12:09:37.54 SWS - - - - Idling
12:09:37.76 LSH - - - - Idling

```

12:09:39.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:09:39.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:09:39.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:09:44.57	SWS	-	-	40	-	VIS int.time changed from 90ms to 40ms.
12:09:47.46	SWS	-	-	-	40	NIR int.time changed from 90ms to 40ms.
12:09:57.36	SWS	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 40ms to 30ms.
12:10:00.90	SWS	-	-	-	30	NIR int.time changed from 40ms to 30ms.
12:10:07.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:10:07.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:10:07.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:10:08.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:10:08.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:10:09.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:10:10.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:10:15.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:10:26.33	---	-	-	-	-	*** orbit 2
12:13:18.55	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of orbit 2 sza 48 ba 35
12:15:18.71	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile ascent
12:15:41.70	---	-	-	-	-	*** climbing to FL 340
12:21:41.44	SWS	-	-	80	-	VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 80ms.
12:21:45.89	SWS	-	-	-	80	NIR int.time changed from 30ms to 80ms.
12:21:48.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:21:48.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:21:48.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:21:49.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:21:50.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:21:50.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:22:10.22	LSH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 90ms to 100ms.
12:22:13.57	LSH	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 90ms to 100ms.
12:22:17.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:22:17.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:22:17.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:22:17.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:22:18.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:22:18.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:22:18.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:22:20.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:22:25.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:22:25.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:22:57.39	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run at FL 349
12:23:05.30	---	-	-	-	-	*** 340
12:23:11.77	---	-	-	-	-	*** in cloud and s
12:23:23.09	---	-	-	-	-	*** cirrus
12:27:10.38	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
12:27:12.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:27:13.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:27:13.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:27:14.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:27:14.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:27:15.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:32:48.28	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
12:36:55.99	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile climb
12:37:23.02	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 3 to FL 350
12:38:13.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:38:13.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:38:13.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:38:15.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:38:15.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:38:16.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:38:49.46	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of profile start of run
12:39:44.98	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 3 and run 3
12:42:51.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:42:51.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:42:51.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:42:53.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:42:53.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:42:53.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:42:54.33	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:43:01.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

12:43:01.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:43:01.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:43:02.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:43:02.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:43:03.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:43:03.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:03.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:06.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:43:06.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:43:26.09	---	-	-	-	-	*** ci above
12:43:45.77	---	-	-	-	-	*** clear below
12:46:55.31	---	-	-	-	-	*** ci quite thin
12:48:51.78	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run 2
12:48:56.70	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 3 rather
12:49:13.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:49:13.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:49:13.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:49:13.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:49:14.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:49:14.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:49:14.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:49:16.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:49:16.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:49:16.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:49:16.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:49:16.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:49:39.27	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
12:49:44.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:49:44.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:49:44.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:49:45.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:49:45.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:49:45.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:49:48.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:51:45.58	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run 3.2 FL 350 51.30
12:54:41.21	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:54:45.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:54:45.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:54:45.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:54:47.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:54:47.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:54:47.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:01:41.27	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
13:01:59.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:01:59.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:01:59.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:02:00.90	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
13:02:04.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:02:04.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:02:04.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:02:05.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:02:05.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:02:06.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:02:06.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:02:07.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:02:07.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:02:07.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:02:59.60	SWS	-	-	60	-	VIS int.time changed from 80ms to 60ms.
13:03:03.20	SWS	-	-	-	60	NIR int.time changed from 80ms to 60ms.
13:03:06.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:03:06.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:03:06.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:03:07.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:03:07.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:03:08.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:03:08.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:03:09.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:04:02.62	---	-	-	-	-	*** profilr descent profile 4
13:08:22.78	SWS	-	-	40	-	VIS int.time changed from 60ms to 40ms.

13:08:26.00	SWS	-	-	-	40	NIR int.time changed from 60ms to 40ms.
13:08:34.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:08:34.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:08:34.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:08:35.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:08:36.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:08:36.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:08:36.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:08:39.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:11:20.63	SWS	-	-	80	-	VIS int.time changed from 40ms to 80ms.
13:11:24.40	SWS	-	-	-	80	NIR int.time changed from 40ms to 80ms.
13:11:26.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:11:26.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:11:26.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:11:27.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:11:27.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:11:28.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:17:19.18	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile interupt
13:17:35.38	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 4 FL 220
13:19:32.04	---	-	-	-	-	*** resatrt profile 4
13:23:17.63	---	-	-	-	-	*** start run FL 200
13:23:25.22	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 4
13:24:21.96	---	-	-	-	-	*** ci above but quite thin
13:31:10.25	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
13:31:13.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:31:13.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:31:13.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:31:14.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:31:14.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:31:14.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:32:42.11	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
13:33:16.79	SWS	-	-	40	-	VIS int.time changed from 80ms to 40ms.
13:33:19.71	SWS	-	-	-	40	NIR int.time changed from 80ms to 40ms.
13:33:22.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:33:22.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:33:22.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:33:23.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:33:24.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:33:24.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:33:36.46	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
13:33:44.19	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
13:34:02.64	---	-	-	-	-	*** orbit 1
13:34:18.58	---	-	-	-	-	*** 55 ba
13:34:23.51	SWS	-	-	20	-	VIS int.time changed from 40ms to 20ms.
13:34:26.05	SWS	-	-	-	10	NIR int.time changed from 40ms to 10ms.
13:34:28.67	SWS	-	-	-	20	NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 20ms.
13:35:13.30	---	-	-	-	-	*** orbit ba 58 sza 49
13:35:39.53	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 20ms to 10ms.
13:35:42.58	SWS	-	-	-	10	NIR int.time changed from 20ms to 10ms.
13:35:45.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:35:45.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:35:45.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:35:46.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:35:47.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:35:47.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:36:02.95	---	-	-	-	-	*** orbit 4
13:37:43.51	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of orbit
13:38:29.97	---	-	-	-	-	*** orbit 5
13:39:04.66	---	-	-	-	-	*** ba 58 sza 50
13:39:38.59	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of orbit
13:39:44.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:39:44.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:39:44.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:39:45.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:39:46.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:39:46.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:40:01.62	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 50ms.
13:40:04.71	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 50ms.
13:40:06.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

13:40:06.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:40:06.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:40:07.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:40:08.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:40:08.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:48:53.60	---	-	-	-	-	*** interrupting profile 5
13:50:44.20	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 5 recomencing
13:55:17.36	SWS	-	-	70	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 70ms.
13:55:20.68	SWS	-	-	80	-	VIS int.time changed from 70ms to 80ms.
13:55:24.11	SWS	-	-	-	80	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 80ms.
13:55:26.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:55:26.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:55:26.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:55:27.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:55:28.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:55:28.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:01:40.19	---	-	-	-	-	*** interrupting profilr at FL 100
14:01:52.47	---	-	-	-	-	*** 1000 ft
14:03:04.59	---	-	-	-	-	*** recomencing pr descent
14:05:56.45	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 50 ft
14:06:39.95	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
14:06:43.00	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
14:06:45.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:06:45.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:06:45.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:06:46.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:06:47.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:06:47.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:07:06.56	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 80ms to 100ms.
14:07:09.50	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 80ms to 100ms.
14:07:10.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:07:10.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:07:10.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:07:11.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:07:12.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:07:12.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:07:14.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:07:15.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:08:12.03	---	-	-	-	-	*** 175
14:10:21.33	---	-	-	-	-	*** actually at 100 ft
14:13:40.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:13:40.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:13:40.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:13:42.00	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
14:13:44.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:13:44.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:13:44.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:13:45.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:13:45.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:13:46.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:13:48.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:13:48.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:13:48.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:16:01.36	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
14:18:24.71	---	-	-	-	-	*** 10f for climb
14:21:37.01	---	-	-	-	-	*** ci above sc sq below
14:21:46.79	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
14:21:56.40	---	-	-	-	-	*** 3.5 f
14:25:11.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:25:12.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:25:12.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:25:13.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:25:13.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:25:13.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:26:54.91	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
14:27:15.40	---	-	-	-	-	*** 176R
14:27:23.45	SWS	-	-	80	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 80ms.
14:27:25.96	SWS	-	-	-	80	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 80ms.
14:27:27.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

14:27:27.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:27:27.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:27:28.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:27:28.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:27:28.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:29:48.80	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
14:31:16.78	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of science
14:31:29.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:31:29.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:31:29.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling

ARIES flight log

 Flight: ~~B31TB~~ B320

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Date: 21/8/07

Operator(s): S.M. NEWMAN

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: Far Northwest Scotland

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
083650		1x60	C	C	70.9	30.9	ON GROUND PRE-FLIGHT
083728		1x60	H	C	71.3	30.8	
083805		1x120	N	C	71.1	30.9	(the pan)
083911		1x60	C	C	71.4	30.9	
083947		1x60	H	C	70.9	30.5	
084326		1x60	C	C	71.1	30.6	
090411		1x60	C	C	71.0	30.8	
090445		1x60	H	C	71.2	31.1	
090533		1x120	Z	O	71.1	31.1	8/8 overcast
090644		1x60	C	C	70.8	31.2	
090722		1x60	H	C	71.1	30.9	
094540		TAKE OFF					
							10:02:30 UTC clock correct
1014							Restarted software
1021							" "
1031							" " (to load script)
105430		1.cal		O	70.6	30.8	1.Cal = 1x60 C, 1x60 H sequence
1059							Restarted software
110130							" "
1105							" "
							Wrote 4.CycleZen1 script but cannot get this to run (Zen, HBB, CBB, Zen, CBB, HBB) - will do cals manually
111755		1x60	C	C	70.7	30.1	Looking down with SWS at Sc
111848		1x60	H	C	70.7	30.8	
111933		120x1	N	C	71.0	30.8	Approaching edge of Sc below
112043		1x60	C	C	70.7	30.3	

ARIES flight log

 Flight: ~~B319~~ B320

page 2 of 5

Date: 2/8/07

Operator(s): S. M. NEUMAN

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes:

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
112131	Transit	1x60	H	C	70.7	30.8	
112210		120x1	N	C	70.6	30.4	Clear below now
112316		1x60	C	"	70.7	30.6	
112354		1x60	H	"	70.7	30.5	
112501		120x1	N	"	70.9	30.7	← no use, in turn (clear below)
113821	R1.1 FL320	1x60	C	"	70.5	30.5	
113855	Abort	1x60	H	"	70.8	30.8	Reports of cloud particles, descent to FL310
114055	R1.1	1x60	C	"	70.9	30.8	
114130	FL310	1x60	H	"	70.5	30.7	
114208		240x1	Z	O	71.1	30.4	Under thin cirrus + contrail
114430		1x60	C	C	70.8	30.6	
114503		1x60	H	C	70.7	30.7	
114545		120x1	Z	O	70.6	30.6	Thin, variable thickness Ci above; clear below
114659		1x60	C	C			
114745		1x60	H	C	70.6	30.6	
114832		120x1	N	C	70.8	30.6	Clear below, beyond edge of S _C below
114940		1x60	C	C	70.9	30.5	
115014		1x60	H	C	70.6	30.6	
115418		1x60	C	C	70.3	30.7	
115456		1x60	H	C	70.7	30.8	(in turn)
115555	R1.2	180xZ	Z	O	70.5	30.3	Thin, wispy overhead
115733	FL310	1x60	C	C	70.6	30.5	
115808		1x60	H	C	71.1	30.7	
115848		120x1	Z	O	70.9	30.0	
115957		1x60	C	C			
11591200 30		1x60	H	C	70.9	30.2	
120112		120x1	N	C	70.7	30.9	Looks clear below, few Cu to S' board
120218		1x60	C	C	70.5	29.9	
120253		1x60	H	C	70.7	30.5	
120341		120x1	Z	O	70.4	30.0	Thicker Ci above by eye
120447		1x60	C	C			

ARIES flight log

Flight: ~~B319~~ B320

page 3 of 5

Date: 2/8/07 Operator(s): S. M. NEWMAN

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: NW Scotland cirrus flight

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
120520	R1.2	1x60	H	C	70.8	30.6	
120629	O1	120x1	Z	O	70.7	30.6	started just before orbit
120726	"	1x60	C	C	70.7	29.7	
120800	"	1x60	H	C	70.9	30.2	
120837	"	240x1	Z	O	70.7	30.4	120930 end of orbit; restart 121027
121046	O2	1x60	C	C	70.6	30.6	
121118		1x60	H	C	70.9	31.0	
121155		240x1	Z	O	70.7	31.0	Variable thickness Ci above
							121319 end of orbit, roll out
121405		1x60	C	C	70.7	30.7	
121438		1x60	H	C	70.7	30.0	
122245	R2	1x60	C	C	70.7	30.8	
122325	R3..	1x60	H	C	70.6	30.2	
122403		240x1	Z	O	71.0	30.6	Reasonably uniform thin Ci overhead
122609		1x60	C	C	70.8	29.9	
122645		1x60	H	C			We are
122726		240x1	N	C	70.9	30.0	Just left of Sc sheet, clear below
122932		1x60	C	C	70.7	30.5	
123006		1x60	H	C	70.5	30.5	
123055		120x1	N	C	70.9	30.7	Clear below 120x60 mistake
		1x60	C				
		1x60	H				
123150		120x1	N	C	70.6	30.2	
123256		1x60	C	"			In turn
123326		1x60	H	"			
123849	R3.1	1x60	C	"			
123924		1x60	H	"	70.7	29.8	
124003		240x1	N	"	70.7	30.5	In cirrus. ~ O/P time for satellite
							Can definitely see Ci above (just above)
124207		1x60	C	"	70.7	30.3	mainly clear below
124249		1x60	H	"	70.6	30.7	

ARIES flight log

 Flight: ~~B319~~ B320

page 4 of 5

Date: 21/8/07 Operator(s): S. M. NEWMAN

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: Far NW Scotland

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
124322		240x1	Z	0	70.1	30.9	Thin Ci visible above, v. thin towards end
124534		1x60	C	C	70.5	30.9	
124608		1x60	H	C	70.8	31.0	
124649		120x1	Z	0	70.4	30.5	v. thin above, few Cu below
1248		1x60	C	C	70.5	30.5	
124830		1x60	H	C	70.7	30.7	end of run; turn
124948		1x60	C	C	70.7	30.7	
125024		1x60	H	C	70.7	30.5	
125136	R3.2	240x1	N	C	70.7	30.6	Clear below, CuSc to s'board
125342	FL350?	1x60	C	C	70.9	30.3	thin Ci above
125417		1x60	H	C			
125454		240x1	Z	0	70.0	31.1	v. thin Ci above
125703		1x60	C	C	70.8	30.0	
125737		1x60	H	C	70.6	30.9	extending run
125820		240x1	Z	0	70.5	30.6	fairly uniform, thin above
130027		1x60	C	C	71.1	29.8	
130107		1x60	H	C	70.8	30.5	
		(time check)					DRS = ARIES spot on 13:09:50
132316	R4	1x60	C	C	70.3	30.4	
132351	FL200	1x60	H	C	70.5	30.7	"reduced density Ci above" - Capt Foster
132434		240x1	Z	0	70.7	30.6	v. thin above, by eye
132643		1x60	C	C	70.9	30.7	
132718		1x60	H	C	70.6	30.4	
132756		120x1	Z	0	70.4	30.8	slightly thicker above? Looks like it
132933		1x60	"	"	70.6	30.3	Had to abort, acquisition froze
133032		1x60	C	0	70.6		↓ not sure about the shutter here
133107		1x60	H	0	70.7	30.4	
133145		2120x1	N	0	70.5	30.7	Clear below, Sc to s'board below
133302		1x60	C	0	70.7	30.5	
133340		1x60	H	0	70.7	30.5	
3421	03	120x1	Z	0	70.6	31.2	orbit 60°

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	21/08/07	Flight	B320	log pages	2
Operator(s)	Pollard		Campaign	CAESAR			
Departure	Cranfield		Arrival	Cranfield			

**System start
MARSS**

Visual pod inspection							X
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers							X
Close all MARSS circuit breakers							X
FERA on				at time	07:48:41		
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	18°C	Ch	18°C	Ch18	17°C	
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20	40°C	
MARSS CPU on				at time	07:52:34		
Initial target temperatures	Hot	288.7	Cold	286.7			
Target heating							X
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***							X
Scanning on (LMD box)				at time	08:18:08		
Scan indication		Monitor)		Visual		X

Deimos

PC U/S

Close all Deimos circuit breakers							X
Turn on Deimos CPU							X
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***							
Start Deimos Software				at time			
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold				
Target heating							
Scan indication		Monitor			Visual		
Weather	Cloud		Precip				
	Surface		Pressure				
	Other						

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC} = t_{DRS} +$.5s	at time	09:04:59			
Brightness temps 'sensible'							
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	345.1	Cold	287.4		
	Deimos:	Hot		Cold			
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B			
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)			
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20		
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)		
	1	31.88	38.60	40.58	42.76		

Power changeover

Headset on before start							
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.						
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)							
Exit Deimos Software (x)							
POWER CHANGEOVER							
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton						
Restart Deimos Software							
System running again							at time

Flight:

B320

KEY

- Duff Data
- Minor Problems
- OK
- Not Fitted
- Fitted, Not Operated

Thermometers

- Cabin Temperature:
- Heimann:
- Deiced Temp:
- Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

- FWVS:
- General Eastern:
- Johnson Williams:
- Nevezorov:
- Total Water Probe:

Cameras

- Downward Facing:
- Forward Facing:
- Rearward Facing:
- Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

- Cruciform GPS:
- GIN Applanix:
- INU Honeywell:
- Radar Altimeter:
- RVSM IAS:
- RVSM Static Pressure:
- XR5 GPS:

Report Created 04/09/2007
15:49:23

Misc Core

- AMTG:
- AVAPS:
- Cabin Pressure:
- Fax machine:
- Printer:
- S9 Static Pressure:
- Satcom C:
- Satcom H:
- Turb Centre-Static:
- Turb Left Right:
- Turb Up-Down:
- Turb Horizontal Chk:
- Turb Vertical Chk:
- Weather Radar:
- DLUs:**
- DLU AERACK:
- DLU BBR Lower:
- DLU BBR Upper:
- DLU Core Chem:
- DLU Core Consoles:
- DLU Port Aft:
- DLU Port Fwd:
- DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

- Lower:**
- BBR (clear) Lower:
- BBR (IR) Lower:
- BBR (red) Lower:
- Upper:**
- BBR (clear) Upper:
- BBR (IR) Upper:
- BBR (red) Upper:
- ARIES:
- DEIMOS:
- IR Camera:
- JNO2 Lower:
- JNO2 Upper:
- JO1D Lower:
- JO1D Upper:
- MARSS:
- SHIMS Lower:
- SHIMS Upper:
- SWS:
- TAFTS:

Last Updated:

Cloud Probes

- 2DC:
- 2DP:
- FFSSP:
- PCASP:
- ADA:
- CCN:
- CDP:
- CIP 100:
- CIP 25:
- CPI:
- CVI:
- SID1:
- SID2:
- Aerosol**
- CPC 3025A:
- Filters 47mm:
- Filters 90mm:
- Neph - Dry:
- Neph - Wet:
- PSAP:
- AMS:
- CPC 3025 (AMS):
- INC:
- VACC:
- CPC 3010A (CVI):

23/08/2007 17:23:29

Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002:
- NOx TE42C:
- Ozone TE49C:
- Ozone TE49:
- SO2 TE43C:
- TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
- TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
- FAGE:
- Formaldehyde:
- NOxy:
- ORAC:
- PAN:
- PERCA:
- Peroxide:
- PTRMS:
- TDLAS (1C):
- WAS Bags:
- WAS Bottles:
- Misc Non-Core**
- CASI/ATM:
- LIDAR:
- LTI:
- SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B320

Date: 21/08/2007

Instruments

1. TWC – status light came on during initial climb, status 4091 DRSU, and stayed on for most of flight until profile down towards Stornoway. Went out at 1345, FL150, TAT= -6degC.
2. GE – Dew Point on HORACE wrong, always warmer than DI (+15C). Sensor swapped yesterday. Requested constants sent to aircraft in flight. These very close to existing ones so didn't make much difference. Possible faulty sensor or could be sampling air from the hold.
3. Lower pyrgeometer – signal dropped sharply when cover retracted then jumping between new (low) level and previous level. Coincided with more noise at 1141 when shutter selected. Possible interference between LBBR shutter and BBRs.
4. FWVS – dew point reading 6280C at FL260. Checked FWVS pc. Lamp set at 0.0 i.e. not on. Set to 8.0, then 4.5 (as in pre-flight instructions), then reading DP=-38C. Data still wrong on HORACE.
5. PCASP – switched off as got cold soaked at FL350.
6. 2DP not good at high altitude & cold, okay otherwise.
7. CIP 100 – came to life briefly
8. TAFTS – u/s fairly soon after take-off. Crashing every 2 seconds. Data from Run 4.
9. Sondes – first sonde's data became intermittent during turn (30deg bank). Decreased to 10 deg bank but didn't improve. Also, flight number B319 sent in messages to Met DB (ie. Instead of B320).
10. DFC – 3 x time stamps on picture. DFC camera worked on yesterday to try and get rid of the “motion sensor alarm” message.

Aircraft

Nil

Cranfield Airport

1. We were Informed pre-flight that Cranfield only has Cat4 fire cover until late afternoon (need Cat6). Dispensation granted for us to depart from Cranfield.

Satcom-H Calls - Nil

ISDN - 3 messages received, 2 with attachments from Met O HQ.

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B320:

Log	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
TAFTS	TAFTS operator does not create a log sheet

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	10 Oct 2007	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

2 x Forward Facing Cameras
2 x Rearward Facing Cameras
1 x Upward Facing Cameras
1 x Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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B320 HR Vis 1200

B320 IR 1200.jpg

B320_cloud image